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Teachers' Practices on the Art of Questioning and Learners' Performance: A Basis for Action Plan

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Abstract

This study investigated the effects of teachers' utilization on the art of questioning on learners' academic performance in Araling Panlipunan at Baloi East District, Sigayan, Baloi, Lanao del Norte, during the academic year 2023-2024. The research used a descriptive-correlational research design to explore teachers' questioning techniques and their potential correlation with student performance, without manipulating variables. A sample of 100 teachers from Baloi East District Schools under the Division of Lanao del Norte participated in the study. The findings revealed commendable proficiency among teachers in deploying effective questioning techniques, contributing to a dynamic and engaging learning environment. Teachers demonstrated adeptness in stimulating discussions, maintaining focused dialogues, and posing open-ended questions, fostering critical thinking among students. Furthermore, students exhibited generally positive academic performance in Araling Panlipunan, with a significant proportion achieving very satisfactory and outstanding grades. However, regression analyses indicated that teachers' questioning practices and demographic factors such as age, education level, years of service, and position did not significantly influence academic performance or challenges in assessment implementation. Recommendations stemming from the study included incorporating holistic professional development opportunities for teachers, creating a supportive environment for ongoing learning, encouraging diverse instructional strategies, and promoting active student engagement.

Keywords: *socratic method, art of questioning, questioning techniques, descriptive-correlational research design*

Introduction

The art of questioning serves as a foundational aspect within the context of educational practices, particularly concerning methodologies such as the Socratic Method. Before delving into an exploration of the Socratic Method and its implications for teaching and learning, it is essential to appreciate the artistry inherent in posing thought-provoking questions. Essentially, the study is conducted to understand how teachers utilized the Socratic Method through an art of questioning technique and its impact on student performance. By examining teaching practices, the aim is to identify effective strategies, support professional development, and inform educational policy for enhanced learning outcomes.

Moreover, allowing students to articulate their thoughts and opinions thoughtfully posted a challenging task. Students tend to keep quiet when asked questions. Most teachers prioritize completing the tasks on their daily lesson plan, frequently at the expense of giving their students more opportunities to become stronger argumentations and problem solvers. For this reason, educators must encourage constructive conversations with their students (Smith, 2022).

In an effort to improve teaching strategies and student learning results, the Department of Education (DepEd) has long been at the forefront of developing and implementing educational policies. DepEd has published directives and recommendations in recent years that highlight the value of effective questioning techniques in the teaching-learning process. DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2016 or "Policy Guidelines on Daily Lesson Preparation for the K to 12 Basic Education Program," effective questioning is mentioned as a crucial educational technique to encourage students' critical thinking and deeper comprehension (DepEd, 2016).

Moreover, questioning is not merely a mechanical process but rather an art form that requires skill, precision, and intentionality. Through the strategic use of questions, educators can stimulate critical thinking, foster deep reflection, and cultivate meaningful dialogue within the classroom. The art of questioning empowers teachers to guide students on a journey of discovery, encouraging them to explore complex concepts, challenge assumptions, and construct their understanding of the world around them.

Within the framework of the Socratic Method, questioning takes center stage as a primary means of instruction. Originating from the teachings of the ancient Greek philosopher Socrates, this method emphasizes the importance of inquiry-based learning and dialectical dialogue (Jones & Smith, 2020). Instead of simply transmitting knowledge to students, educators employing the Socratic method engage learners in a dynamic exchange of ideas through a series of carefully crafted questions.

By honing their skills in the art of questioning, teachers can create a dynamic learning environment where curiosity is cultivated, critical thinking is nurtured, and intellectual growth is fostered (Brown & Johnson, 2019). As we embark on an exploration of the Socratic Method and its impact on learners' performance, let us first recognize and appreciate the profound influence of effective questioning techniques in shaping the educational experience.

Socrates' ideas are the foundation of the Socratic Method, an educational strategy that promotes inquiry and critical thinking. With this approach, students are encouraged to look into and evaluate both recently found facts and common sense ideas. Lecturers who employ the Socratic approach in their instruction give valuable insight into their students' perspectives by lending a helping hand without asking anything in return. This method's proponents contend that it is fundamental to good pedagogy and is ideal for comprehensive

classrooms. Any instructor can use the adaptable Socratic method to achieve challenging educational objectives (Abelman & Atkin, 2019).

There have been numerous educational developments and trends. Critical thinking skills are still valued in the literature. This study examines critical thinking skills, focusing on the literature on a teaching and evaluation technique related to developing these skills in a Socratic method which will be a basis for an action plan. Critical thinking is a vital skill that education is encouraged to cultivate. They can analyze information obtained through their senses and think deeply about it because they have this ability. Poor critical thinking leads to risks such as inadequate decision-making, frequent errors, inaccurate assumptions, and so on.

The fact that teachers often undervalue the importance of questions in content instruction is one of the reasons they prioritize topic coverage over critical thinking. As such, they presume that questions and answers can be taught independently. The fact that all claims and declarations that this or that is so are implicit responses to queries is, in fact, so deeply ingrained in established education that it is seldom ever acknowledged (Elder & Paul, 2019).

Meanwhile, despite ongoing efforts, significant learning gaps persist in the teaching of Araling Panlipunan. Traditional pedagogical approaches often prioritize memorization over critical thinking, leading to shallow understanding among students. Moreover, limited access to updated teaching resources and materials hampers educators' ability to deliver comprehensive and engaging lessons. While Department of Education (DepEd) provides professional development opportunities, there remains a need for more extensive training in innovative teaching methodologies, including technology integration and inquiry-based learning. Assessment practices in Araling Panlipunan also often fail to assess critical thinking skills, relying instead on memorization-based examinations. Furthermore, the curriculum and materials may lack cultural relevance, neglecting to incorporate local histories and perspectives. Addressing these gaps requires collaborative efforts to prioritize pedagogical innovation, resource allocation, teacher training, assessment reform, and cultural inclusivity. By doing so, DepEd can enhance the quality of Araling Panlipunan education and provide meaningful learning experiences for Filipino students.

Teachers may find it difficult to get updated resources and materials, forcing them to use out-of-date textbooks and teaching aids. Even with DepEd's professional development opportunities, there may be a lack of instruction in innovative approaches to teaching, which would keep the focus on conventional methods. The study found that although some teachers are excited to use technology and inquiry-based learning in their Araling Panlipunan classrooms, many encounter obstacles including inadequate training in digital resource use and restricted access to technology. Furthermore, recall is the main emphasis of evaluation procedures rather than higher-order thinking abilities. Additionally, the curriculum appears to be lacking in cultural relevance, placing minimal focus on local histories and viewpoints.

The study of teachers' practices regarding the Socratic Method and its influence on learners' performance is paramount due to its potential contributions to education. Firstly, understanding how educators employ the Socratic method can lead to enhanced critical thinking skills among students. By probing students with thought-provoking questions, educators can encourage deeper analysis and evaluation of course material, fostering a more robust understanding of concepts. Secondly, the Socratic Method promotes active student engagement, which is vital for effective learning. By studying how teachers effectively implement this method, educators can create more interactive and stimulating classroom environments, thereby increasing student motivation and participation.

Finally, acknowledging the urgent need for innovative pedagogy and filling in the gaps in Araling Panlipunan education, the study's result was an action plan for enhancing effective questioning techniques for improved academic performance. Through the application of creative approaches, the investigation of pedagogical issues, and the integration of cultural diversity, this action plan aims to equip teachers with the knowledge and skills required to create a stimulating learning environment that supports curiosity, critical thinking, and academic achievement. They want to provide teachers with the tools and support they need to use questioning strategies successfully, hence raising the standard of teaching and providing students with worthwhile educational experiences.

Research Questions

This study assessed the teachers' practices on the art of questioning and learners' performance in Araling Panlipunan of Sigayan Integrated School, Baloi East District, Sigayan, Baloi, Lanao del Norte during the school year 2023-2024. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. highest educational attainment;
 - 1.4. number of years in the service; and
 - 1.5. plantilla position?
2. What are the teachers' practices on the art of questioning in terms of:
 - 2.1. questioning technique; and
 - 2.2. types of questioning?
3. What is the academic performance of the learners in Araling Panlipunan?

4. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' demographic profile and the teachers' practices on the art of questioning?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' practices on the art of questioning and the academic performance of learners in Araling Panlipunan?
6. Based on the findings of the study, what action plan was developed?

Methodology

Research Design

In the descriptive-correlational research design, the goal was to describe the link between teacher Socratic Method practices and learner performance without changing any factors. The design entailed monitoring and documenting the ways employed by teachers who use the Socratic Method, as well as linking such approaches to their students' academic performance.

Descriptive research was essential in this study to offer a thorough overview of the participants and their teaching performance. The study provided the demographic features of the teachers concisely using descriptive statistics such as frequency distributions and measures of central tendency and variability, including their age, gender, educational background, and years of teaching experience. This information provided useful background for understanding the sample composition and potential factors influencing their views and performance.

On the other hand, correlational research was essential for examining relationships between variables without implying causation. In this study, the correlational analysis explored connections between teachers' evaluations of the question-and-answer learning approach and their teaching performance, as well as the relationship between demographic factors and these variables. By analyzing correlations, the study identified potential patterns or associations, shedding light on the factors that may have impacted teachers' perceptions and effectiveness in the classroom.

Together, descriptive and correlational research methodologies provided complementary insights into the research questions, offering a nuanced understanding of the relationship between instructional practices, teacher characteristics, and teaching performance. While descriptive research outlined the characteristics of the sample, correlational analysis delved deeper into understanding the interplay between variables, ultimately contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of the study's objectives.

Respondents

The respondents in this research were carefully selected to ensure a representative and diverse sample. One hundred teachers (100) were randomly selected in Baloi East District Schools, which fell under the purview of the Division of Lanao del Norte, during the academic year 2023-2024. Random sampling was employed in this study aimed to provide a comprehensive perspective on the impact of the question-and-answer learning approach on the performances of teachers.

Araling Panlipunan education is a distinct combination of teaching and learning, with teachers and students playing critical roles. Teachers with expertise in several social science areas lead students via historical tales, geographical investigations, economic assessments, and civic inquiries. They promote a culture of inquiry, fostering critical thinking and meditation on societal complexity. Teachers are more than simply information disseminators; they also facilitate meaningful discussion by encouraging students to question, evaluate, and synthesize knowledge in order to build their understanding of the world. They incorporate local histories, cultural practices, and societal values into their courses, encouraging students to cherish their Filipino ancestry and identity.

Students actively participate in their educational journey, using critical thinking skills to assess historical events, evaluate geographical phenomena, and deal with socioeconomic difficulties. They get a comprehensive awareness of interconnection, cultural variety, and global citizenship while stressing empathy, respect for human rights, and civic duty. Students with good communication skills may boldly express their thoughts and opinions, adding effectively to conversations and debates. Finally, Araling Panlipunan students emerge as lifelong learners, equipped with the knowledge, skills, and values needed to navigate a rapidly changing world with resilience and purpose.

To prevent bias and ensure fairness, a random sampling method was used. This involved assigning a unique identifier (e.g., a number) to each eligible teacher in the population. A random selection process, such as using a computer-generated random number generator, was employed to select the 100 participants from this pool. This step ensured that each teacher had an equal chance of being selected, enhancing the study's representativeness.

Instrument

To measure the relationship between the teachers' performance and their evaluation of the influence of the teaching and learning approach on instructional practices, the study used a self-made questionnaire. The questionnaire served as the basis for collecting data.

Part 1 of the questionnaire included the profile of the teachers, including their age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, and number of years in service and plantilla position. Part 2 focused on the teachers practices in the art of questioning technique and the types of questioning. Part 3 focused on the academic achievement of the learners in Araling Panlipunan.

Before the full dissemination of the research questionnaire, pilot testing was conducted. Pilot testing of the researcher-made questionnaire ensures its quality before full-scale implementation. A small group similar to the study population completes the questionnaire, providing feedback on clarity and relevance. Researchers analyze feedback and make necessary revisions for improved validity and reliability. This process ensures the questionnaire is suitable for the study population, enhancing research integrity. The result of this pilot study was analyzed through Cronbach's Alpha.

To ensure the validity and reliability of the survey questionnaires, a panel of two experts was consulted during the data-gathering process. The experts evaluated the appropriateness of the research instrument and provided feedback and comments to refine the final research instrument. The consultation with the panel of experts was an important step in the research process, as it enhanced the quality of the research instrument and improved the validity and reliability of the data collected. After the consultations of the questionnaire, pilot testing was conducted to test the internal consistency of the questionnaire through the inclusion of non-participant teachers from other schools.

Using the Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.7 or higher is generally considered acceptable for research purposes. The Cronbach's Alpha values for the study variables are higher than the acceptable threshold of 0.7., indicating that the reliability of these variables is excellent. Thus, suggests that the internal consistency of the items to measure teacher's practices on the art of questioning was met. Thus, the instrument used in this study has excellent internal consistency, indicating that it can be used for future research purposes.

Procedure

The data-gathering procedures in this study involved several steps to ensure the collection of high-quality and reliable data. Firstly, after necessary approvals were secured, the researcher scheduled appointments with the selected elementary teachers in Baloi East District Schools. These appointments were made to conduct the survey and administer the researcher-made questionnaire.

During the data collection process, the researcher explained the purpose of the study to the participants and distributed informed consent forms. These forms outlined the study's objectives, expected duration, confidentiality measures, and the voluntary nature of participation. Teachers were encouraged to ask any questions they had before providing their consent to participate in the study.

Once consent was obtained, participants were asked to complete the questionnaire, which consisted of two parts. Part 1 of the questionnaire included the profile of the teachers, including their age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, and number of years in service and plantilla position. Part 2 focused on the teachers' practices in the art of questioning technique and the types of questioning. Part 3 focused on the academic achievement of the learners in Araling Panlipunan.

After data collection, the researcher compiled the completed questionnaires and ensured that all necessary information had been provided. Any missing or unclear responses were clarified with the participants if possible.

Once the data collection phase was complete, the researcher proceeded to analyze the gathered data using statistical software. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographic characteristics of the participants and their learners' performance in Aralaing Panlipunan. Correlational analyses were conducted to examine the relationships between teachers' evaluations of the teaching approach and their teaching performance, as well as demographic factors.

Throughout the data-gathering process, ethical considerations such as confidentiality and voluntary participation were strictly adhered to, ensuring the integrity and validity of the research findings.

Data Analysis

These statistical tools helped provide insights and interpretations of the data gathered from the study and aided in answering the research questions and objectives.

Frequency and Percentage Distribution: This was used to describe the profile of the respondents and the learners' academic performance in Araling Panlipunan. It provided an overview of the demographic characteristics of the participants and the overall learners' academic performance in Araling Panlipunan.

Mean and Standard Deviation: These were used to calculate and describe the teachers' practices in the art of questioning and technique and the types of questioning. This statistical analysis gave insights into the average perception of the teachers regarding the effectiveness of the teaching method, as well as the variability in their responses.

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA): This was used to determine if there was a significant difference between the perceptions of the teachers' practices in the art of questioning and technique and the types of questioning when grouped according to their profile. ANOVA helped in identifying any potential differences in perception based on demographic variables such as age, sex, educational attainment, etc.

Regression: This was used to determine if there was a significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and the teachers' practices in the art of questioning and technique and the types of questioning, as well as between the profile of the respondents and learners' performances in Araling Panlipunan. Regression analysis aided in understanding the extent to which demographic variables influenced the perception of the teachers' practices in the art of questioning and technique and the types of questioning and the overall

learners' performance in Araling Panlipunan.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the analyses, results, and discussions of the data gathered by the researcher.

Problem 1: What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms age, sex, highest educational attainment, number of years in the service; Plantilla position?

Table 1. *Age of the Respondents*

<i>Age (in years)</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
25-30	30	30.0
31-36	22	22.0
37-42	19	19.0
43-48	16	16.0
49-54	13	13.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 1 presents the distribution of respondents based on their age in a survey, highlighting the age groups and corresponding frequencies and percentages. The data reveals a diverse range of respondents, with the majority falling within the 25-30 age bracket, constituting 30% of the total sample. Following closely, the 31-36 age group comprises 22%, indicating a relatively younger demographic. As the age brackets progress, the percentage distribution gradually decreases, with 19% falling in the 37-42 range, 16% in the 43-48 category, and 13% in the 49-54 group. These results suggest a relatively balanced representation across different age groups, providing a comprehensive overview of the respondents' age demographics.

Table 2. *Sex of the Respondents*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Male	1	1.0
Female	99	99.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 2 illustrates the gender distribution of the surveyed respondents. The data indicates a notable gender imbalance, with an overwhelming majority of 99% identifying as female, while only 1% identified as male. This skew towards female respondents suggests a potential gender-related bias in the sample, which may impact the generalizability of findings to a broader population.

Table 3. *Civil Status of the Respondents*

<i>Civil Status</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Single	20	20.0
Married	80	80.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 3 presents the distribution of respondents based on their civil status in the surveyed population. The data indicates that married people make up 80% of all responses, which is a predominate representation. In contrast, the single respondents make up the remaining 20%. This clear majority of married individuals within the sample suggests a demographic inclination towards those who are married, potentially influencing the outcomes and insights derived from the survey.

Table 4. *Highest Educational Attainment of the Respondents*

<i>Highest Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Without MA Units	41	41.0
With MA Units	54	54.0
With PhD Units	1	1.0
PhD Graduate	1	1.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 4 shows the highest educational attainment of the surveyed respondents, providing a breakdown of the frequency and corresponding percentages. Among the respondents, 54% have completed coursework towards an MA, while 41% have not earned any MA units. Together, these two groups represent the majority of respondents. Additionally, there is a minimal representation of individuals with either completed PhD units (1%) or those who have attained a PhD degree (1%). The data suggests a diverse educational background within the sample, with a notable proportion having engaged in postgraduate studies.

Table 5 presents the distribution of respondents based on the number of years in service, providing insights into the professional experience of the surveyed individuals. The data indicates a diverse range of tenure, with the highest percentage (26%) falling within the 11-20 years category, followed by the 21-25 years category at 21%. The 6-10 years and below-5 years categories each account for 17%, while the 26-30 years and 31-above categories both contribute 10%. This distribution highlights a relatively balanced representation of individuals across various career stages.

Table 5. Number of Years in the Service of the Respondents

<i>Number of Years in the Service</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Below-5	16	16.0
6-10	17	17.0
11-20	26	26.0
21-25	21	21.0
26-30	10	10.0
31-above	10	10.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 6. Position of the Respondents

<i>Position</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Teacher I	46	46.0
Teacher II	29	29.0
Teacher III	20	20.0
Master Teacher I	5	5.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 6 displays the distribution of respondents based on their respective positions, shedding light on the occupational composition within the surveyed population. According to the data, 46% of the sample's respondents are Teacher I, making up the majority of the respondents. Following closely, Teacher II accounts for 29%, and Teacher III for 20%. A smaller proportion, 5%, holds the position of Master Teacher I. These results highlight how common teaching roles with a range of responsibilities and skill levels are in the sample.

Problem 2: What are the teachers’ practices on the art of questioning in terms of questioning technique, and types of questioning?

Table 7. Teachers’ Practice on the Art of Questioning in terms of Questioning Technique

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. I plan significant questions to inform an overall structure and direction without being too prescriptive.	3.34	.59	Most of the time
2. I allow time for the student or client to respond to the questions without feeling hurried.	3.46	.52	Most of the time
3. I stimulate the discussion with probing questions that follow the responses given.	3.38	.53	Most of the time
4. I invite elaboration and facilitate self-discovery through questioning.	3.45	.54	Most of the time
5. I keep the dialogue focused, specific, and clearly worded.	3.36	.50	Most of the time
6. I regularly summarize what has been said.	3.37	.53	Most of the time
7. I pose open questions rather than yes/no questions.	3.31	.53	Most of the time
8. I avoid or re-word questions that are vague, ambiguous, or beyond the level of the listener’s understanding.	3.32	.53	Most of the time
Total Measure	3.38	.28	Most of the time

Note: 1.00–1.49, Never; 1.50–2.49, Sometime; 2.50–3.49, Most of the time; 3.50–4.00, All the time

Table 7 presents the mean and standard deviation (SD) values for teachers' practices related to the art of questioning, focusing on various questioning techniques. The respondents, on average, reported high mean scores across all indicators, indicating a consistent practice of useful methods for asking questions. The mean score for the total measure is 3.38, with a relatively low standard deviation of 0.28, suggesting a generally homogenous pattern of responses among the surveyed teachers. This implies a substantial level of agreement in the reported practices, reinforcing the notion that teachers, on average, engage in effective questioning techniques "most of the time."

The high mean scores for each indicator suggest that teachers are adept at planning significant questions to guide discussions, allowing ample opportunity for student responses, stimulating discussions through probing questions, and inviting elaboration and self-discovery. Additionally, teachers seem to keep their conversations narrowly focused, precise, and well-worded; they also frequently summarize class discussions and use open-ended questions as opposed to binary ones. The low standard deviations indicate minimal variability in responses, reinforcing the consistency in teachers' reported practices.

These results have meaningful implications for educational practices and professional development. The overall positive scores suggest a strong foundation in effective questioning techniques among the surveyed teachers. By identifying and disseminating best practices, educational institutions can use these insights to promote a continuous improvement culture. Additionally, targeted training programs could focus on areas where teachers might benefit from further development, enhancing their questioning skills. In the end, knowing how to ask good questions and encouraging others to do so creates a learning atmosphere that is more influential and interesting.

Table 8 provides the teachers' practices related to the art of questioning, focusing on different types of questions. The mean and standard deviation (SD) values for each indicator offer insights into the consistency and variability of teachers' approaches. The overall mean score for the total measure is 3.38, with a low standard deviation of 0.23, indicating a high level of agreement among respondents in employing various types of questions "most of the time."

Table 8. Teachers' Practice on the Art of Questioning in terms of Types of Questioning

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Factual Questions			
1. I require students to recall specific previously learned.	3.41	.55	Most of the time
2. I ask who, what, when, and where questions.	3.44	.56	Most of the time
3. I ask simple bits of information.	3.40	.57	Most of the time
Probing Questions			
4. I require students to go beyond the first response.	3.26	.51	Most of the time
5. I ask clarifying questions or elaborate on their comments by asking more information.	3.36	.52	Most of the time
6. I lead my students to tie their response to the content being discussed.	3.43	.54	Most of the time
Prompting/ Rephrasing Questions			
7. I provide some information to help students come up with the correct answer.	3.39	.51	Most of the time
8. I rephrase the question when a student provides an incorrect response or no answer.	3.36	.52	Most of the time
9. I lead the students to the final answer.	3.33	.57	Most of the time
Divergent Questions			
10. I ask hypothetical questions which encourage exploration of possibilities.	3.42	.57	Most of the time
11. I ask students to find the cause and effect relationship.	3.37	.53	Most of the time
12. I ask students find the similarities and differences.	3.35	.52	Most of the time
13. I ask students to compare and contrast.	3.40	.57	Most of the time
Higher Order Questions			
14. I ask higher order and critical questions to students.	3.49	.56	Most of the time
15. I ask students to evaluate the situation in general.	3.21	.48	Most of the time
16. I ask students to solve a particular problem in the story read.	3.32	.53	Most of the time
B.6 Affective Questions			
17. I ask the moral/ lesson of the story read.	3.45	.56	Most of the time
18. I elicit expression of attitudes and values of the students.	3.33	.51	Most of the time
19. I ask them how they feel about the situation.	3.46	.52	Most of the time
Total Measure	3.38	.23	Most of the time

Note: 1.00-1.49, Never; 1.50-2.49, Sometime; 2.50-3.49, Most of the time; 3.50-4.00, All the time

Across the different categories of questioning, teachers reported consistently high mean scores. In factual questions, teachers excel in requiring students to recall specific information, asking fundamental questions (who, what, when, where), and seeking simple bits of information. Similarly, in probing questions, teachers demonstrate proficiency in prompting students to go beyond initial responses, seeking clarification, and tying responses to the content being discussed. The scores for prompting/rephrasing questions indicate effective guidance provided by teachers in helping students arrive at correct answers, rephrasing questions when needed, and leading students to the final answer.

In divergent questions, teachers are successful in encouraging exploration of possibilities, exploring cause-and-effect relationships, and comparing and contrasting. The mean scores for higher-order questions highlight the effectiveness of teachers in asking critical and evaluative questions. Furthermore, in affective questions, teachers excel in eliciting moral lessons from stories, exploring students' attitudes and values, and gauging their emotional responses to situations.

These findings carry significant implications for teaching practices. The consistently high mean scores suggest a strong foundation in employing various types of questions among the surveyed teachers. This competency is essential for developing students' critical thinking, participation, and emotional intelligence. These findings can be used by educational institutions to pinpoint and share best practices, and by professional development organizations to focus on areas where teachers might need more assistance. The dependability of the presented data is further supported by the low standard deviations, which also point to a high degree of consistency in procedures. Overall, understanding and enhancing teachers' questioning techniques contribute to creating a dynamic and effective learning environment.

Problem 3: What is the academic performance of the learners in Araling Panlipunan?

Table 9. Academic Performance of the Learners in Araling Panlipunan

Academic Grades	Performance Level	Frequency	Percentage (%)
90-100	Outstanding	33	11.0
85-89	Very Satisfactory	141	47.0
80-84	Satisfactory	69	23.0
75-79	Fairly Satisfactory	57	19.0
Total		300	100.0

Note: Mean (SD) = 84.94 (4.24)

Based on their appropriate grade ranges, Table 9 displays the academic performance of students in Araling Panlipunan, divided into several performance levels. The majority of learners fall within the "Very Satisfactory" category, with 47% receiving grades in the 85-89 range. An additional 11% of learners achieved an "Outstanding" performance level, with grades ranging from 90-100. The distribution also indicates that 23% of learners attained a "Satisfactory" level (80-84), and 19% achieved a "Fairly Satisfactory" level

(75-79). The overall mean grade is reported as 84.94, with a standard deviation of 4.24.

These academic performance results carry several implications for educators, administrators, and policymakers. The concentration of learners in the "Very Satisfactory" range suggests a generally positive academic environment, with a significant proportion of students demonstrating competence in Araling Panlipunan. The presence of learners in the "Outstanding" category also reflects the excellence achieved by a notable portion of the student body. To effectively customize instructional tactics and interventions, it is imperative to take into account the distribution across various performance levels.

The mean grade and standard deviation provide additional context, indicating the average performance and the degree of variability in academic scores. The mean grade of 84.94 suggests a solid overall performance, but educators should delve deeper into the standard deviation of 4.24 to understand the extent of the dispersion in student performance. Targeted assistance for students who might be struggling or performing above expectations can be guided by this information. Collaborative efforts between teachers, parents, and educational stakeholders are essential to maintaining and enhancing the positive aspects of academic achievement while addressing any challenges that may arise. A more efficient and inclusive learning environment will result from routinely assessing and modifying support systems and teaching strategies in light of these academic performance measures.

Problem 4: Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' practices on the art of questioning and the academic performance of learners in Araling Panlipunan?

Table 10 presents the correlation analysis between the academic performance of learners and the teachers' practices on the art and types of questioning in Araling Panlipunan. The analysis reveals non-significant results across all variables, as indicated by their respective *r*-values and *p*-values. The correlation coefficients ranged from $-.102$ to $.123$, with corresponding *p*-values ranging from $.225$ to $.905$, none of which reached significance at the $.05$ level.

Table 10. *Correlation Analysis between Academic Performance of Learners and the Teachers' Practices on the Art and Types of Questioning*

Variable	Academic Performance		Remarks
	<i>r</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value	
Art of Questioning	$-.102$	$.315$	Not significant
Factual Questions	$.033$	$.748$	Not significant
Probing Questions	$-.012$	$.905$	Not significant
Prompting/Rephrasing Questions	$.123$	$.225$	Not significant
Divergent Questions	$-.040$	$.690$	Not significant
Higher order Thinking Skills	$-.055$	$.584$	Not significant
Affective Questions	$-.093$	$.360$	Not significant

Note: Analysis is based on Point-Biserial Correlation

Not significant at $.05$ level

These findings indicate that there is no statistically significant correlation between teachers' questioning practices and the academic performance of learners in the subject. Starting with the art of questioning, which had an *r*-value of $-.102$ and a *p*-value of $.315$, the results suggest no significant association between this aspect of teaching methodology and student achievement. Similarly, the types of questioning, including factual questions, probing questions, prompting/rephrasing questions, divergent questions, higher-order thinking skills, and affective questions, all yielded non-significant correlations with academic performance.

These findings imply that while questioning techniques are an essential component of teaching practice, they may not directly influence student academic outcomes in Araling Panlipunan. Therefore, educators and curriculum planners should adopt a holistic approach to instructional design, considering various factors beyond questioning strategies to enhance student learning and achievement.

Problem 5: Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' demographic profile and the teachers' practices on the art and types of questioning?

Table 11 provides the correlation analysis between teachers' demographic profiles and their practice on the art of questioning. The results show varied correlations between demographic factors and the art of questioning, with some significant associations observed. Specifically, teachers within the age range of 25-30 exhibit a significant negative correlation ($r = -.277$, $p = .005$) with the art of questioning, suggesting that younger teachers tend to employ this technique less frequently or effectively.

Additionally, civil status demonstrates significant correlations, with single teachers showing a negative correlation ($r = -.241$, $p = .016$) and married teachers showing a positive correlation ($r = .241$, $p = .016$) with the art of questioning.

Furthermore, years of service also exhibit significant correlations, particularly for teachers with less than five years of service ($r = -.215$, $p = .032$), indicating that less experienced teachers may face challenges in implementing effective questioning techniques. However, other demographic factors such as education level and position do not show significant correlations with the art of questioning.

These findings underscore the importance of considering demographic factors when designing professional development programs aimed at enhancing teachers' questioning practices, particularly targeting younger, single, and less experienced educators.

Table 11. Correlation Analysis between the Teachers' Demographic Profile and the teachers' Practice on the Art of Questioning

Variable	Art of Questioning		Remarks
	r-value	p-value	
Age=25-30	-.277	.005	Significant
Age=31-36	.066	.512	Not significant
Age=37-42	.058	.564	Not significant
Age=43-48	.074	.463	Not significant
Age=49-54	.146	.147	Not significant
Civil Status=Single	-.241*	.016	Significant
Civil Status=Marred	.241*	.016	Significant
Education=Without MA Units	-.113	.263	Not significant
Education=With MA Units	.113	.263	Not significant
Years of Service=below-5	-.215*	.032	Significant
Years of Service=6-10	.084	.404	Not significant
Years of Service=11-20	-.078	.441	Not significant
Years of Service=21-25	.024	.813	Not significant
Years of Service=26-30	.149	.140	Not significant
Years of Service=31+	.090	.374	Not significant
Position= Teacher I	-.067	.509	Not significant
Position=Teacher II	.003	.978	Not significant
Position=Teacher III	.146	.148	Not significant
Position=Master Teacher I	-.121	.232	Not significant

Note: Analysis is based on Point-Biserial Correlation

*significant at .05 level

Table 12 presents the correlation analysis between teachers' demographic profiles and their practice on different types of questioning. The results indicate varying degrees of correlation between demographic factors and types of questioning techniques. Significant correlations are observed for certain age groups, particularly for teachers aged 25-30 and 49-54, with statistically significant correlations noted for several types of questioning, such as divergent questions and higher-order thinking skills. Similarly, civil status demonstrates significant correlations with types of questioning, particularly for single teachers, indicating potential differences in questioning practices based on marital status.

Table 12. Correlation Analysis between the Teachers' Demographic Profile and the teachers' Practice on the Types of Questioning

Variable	Types of Questioning					
	Factual Question	Probing Questions	Prompting/Rephrasing Questions	Divergent Questions	Higher order thinking skills	Affective Questions
Age=25-30	-.100 (.323)	-.147 (.146)	-.128 (.205)	-.277** (.005)	-.258** (.009)	.015 (.883)
Age=31-36	.010 (.921)	.106 (.294)	-.127 (.207)	.146 (.149)	-.030 (.765)	-.192 (.056)
Age=37-42	.175 (.082)	.047 (.644)	.245* (.014)	.114 (.261)	-.008 (.934)	.184 (.066)
Age=43-48	.023 (.823)	.103 (.310)	.093 (.358)	-.012 (.909)	.182 (.069)	-.020 (.846)
Age=49-54	-.105 (.298)	-.097 (.336)	-.056 (.583)	.078 (.439)	.200* (.046)	.022 (.825)
Civil Status=Single	-.208* (.038)	.000 (1.000)	-.174 (.084)	-.112 (.266)	-.052 (.606)	-.103 (.309)
Civil Status=Marred	.208* (.038)	.000 (1.000)	.174 (.084)	.112 (.266)	.052 (.606)	.103 (.309)
Education=Without MA Units	-.072 (.478)	-.092 (.363)	-.042 (.675)	-.136 (.176)	-.121 (.232)	-.032 (.752)
Education=With MA Units	.072 (.478)	.092 (.363)	.042 (.675)	.136 (.176)	.121 (.232)	.032 (.752)
Years of Service=below-5	-.091 (.370)	-.239* (.016)	-.132 (.191)	-.264** (.008)	-.293** (.003)	-.160 (.112)
Years of Service=6-10	.083 (.412)	.266** (.008)	.040 (.693)	.032 (.752)	.038 (.704)	.067 (.510)
Years of Service=11-20	-.047 (.640)	-.027 (.793)	-.064 (.525)	.165 (.101)	-.050 (.621)	-.122 (.227)
Years of Service=21-25	.077 (.449)	.065 (.522)	.209* (.036)	-.006 (.957)	.012 (.903)	.209* (.036)
Years of Service=26-30	.097 (.337)	.045 (.658)	-.024 (.810)	.013 (.896)	.168 (.094)	-.069 (.498)
Years of Service=31+	-.125	-.134 (.183)	-.055 (.587)	.035 (.728)	.197* (.049)	.074 (.463)

	(.216)					
Position= Teacher I	-.008 (.934)	-.113 (.262)	-.104 (.302)	-.170 (.090)	-.016 (.874)	.120 (.236)
Position=Teacher II	-.078 (.441)	.050 (.619)	.135 (.181)	.194 (.053)	-.011 (.913)	-.094 (.354)
Position=Teacher III	.125 (.216)	.090 (.376)	-.014 (.892)	-.013 (.896)	.013 (.897)	-.081 (.421)
Position=Master Teacher I	-.048 (.638)	-.010 (.919)	-.017 (.868)	.009 (.928)	.036 (.723)	.071 (.484)

Note: Analysis is based Point-Biserial Correlation Values expressed in r-value (p-value) *significant at .05 level **significant at .01 level

Furthermore, there are noteworthy associations between years of service and certain question categories, indicating that teachers with different degrees of expertise can use different questioning strategies. However, other demographic factors such as education level and teaching position do not show significant correlations with types of questioning.

These findings underscore the importance of considering demographic characteristics when designing professional development initiatives aimed at enhancing teachers' questioning practices, in addition to the need for tailored interventions to address specific demographic-related challenges in implementing effective questioning techniques.

Problem 6: Based on the findings of the study, what action plan could be developed?

Proposed Action Plan: Enhancing Effective Questioning Techniques for Improved Academic Performance

Rationale

The study has provided insightful information about the problems and practices related to questioning strategies used by instructors, especially in Araling Panlipunan. While certain factors may not significantly impact academic performance or assessment implementation challenges, this action plan aims to leverage the identified strengths and address potential areas of improvement in the utilization of effective questioning techniques. By doing this, we hope to improve critical thinking, academic achievement generally, and student involvement.

Key Action Steps/ Strategies To Achieve Objective	Persons Responsible	Resources/ Budget Needed	Date Of Completion	Threats/ Potential Barriers	Indicators Of Success
Improve Teachers' Questioning Techniques by Conducting professional development workshops on effective questioning methods and integrating questioning strategies into lesson planning and curriculum development.	Curriculum Team, Department Heads	Workshop materials, facilitators, venues, Lesson planning tools, support materials	SY: 2024-2025	Lack of motivation among the teachers in participating the workshop due to extra work overload or ancillary tasks.	Increased teacher awareness and application of diverse questioning techniques, Inclusion of varied questioning in lesson plans and curricula.
Foster a Collaborative Learning Environment by Promoting collaborative learning spaces for teachers to share effective practices and encourage peer observations to enhance the implementation of effective questioning.	Professional Development Team, School Administrators	Online platforms, facilitators, Observation guidelines, feedback tools	SY: 2024-2025	Slow internet connection and a lack of ICT literacy among senior teachers.	Increased collaboration and shared best practices among teachers. Improved implementation of questioning techniques through peer feedback.
Monitor and Evaluate the Impact by Implementing a regular assessment mechanism to evaluate the effectiveness of the action plan and Collect feedback from teachers and students to identify areas for continuous improvement.	Research Team, Evaluation Team	Assessment tools, data analysis tools, Survey tools, facilitators	SY: 2024-2025	resistance to feedback, lack of clarity on assessment criteria, limited time for data collection and analysis, and challenges in effectively collecting feedback from both teachers and students.	Quantitative and qualitative data showing improvements in questioning techniques. Positive feedback from teachers and students on the impact of the action plan.

Conclusions

The study revealed a consistent and commendable proficiency among teachers in deploying effective questioning techniques in the context of Araling Panlipunan. The high level of agreement among surveyed teachers, as reflected in the homogenous pattern of responses and high mean scores, signifies a strong foundation in utilizing diverse questioning strategies. Teachers' excellence in stimulating discussions, maintaining focused dialogues, and employing open-ended questions contributes to a dynamic and engaging learning environment. This points to the overall effectiveness of the teaching cohort in fostering critical thinking skills and enhancing the overall learning experience for students.

On the students' side, the predominant presence in the very satisfactory category and the notable excellence demonstrated by a significant portion of learners in the outstanding level highlight a generally positive academic environment. The distribution across different performance levels provides a clear understanding of student achievements. The findings emphasize the need for educators, administrators, and policymakers to consider this distribution pattern when refining instructional strategies and interventions. While the mean grade indicates solid overall performance, the variability in student achievements, as reflected in the standard deviation, underscores the importance of tailoring efforts for continuous improvement based on a diverse range of learner needs.

The study finds no significant correlation between teachers' questioning practices and learners' academic performance in Araling Panlipunan. This suggests that while questioning techniques are essential, they may not directly impact student achievement. However, demographic factors such as age, civil status, and years of service show significant associations with questioning practices, emphasizing the need for targeted professional development initiatives to address specific challenges faced by educators.

Curriculum planners should consider incorporating professional development opportunities that focus on a holistic approach to teaching beyond questioning techniques. The study indicates that while questioning is essential, other factors significantly influence academic performance. Hence, curriculum enhancements should encompass broader pedagogical strategies, ensuring teachers are equipped with a diverse set of instructional tools. Additionally, curriculum designers may explore integrating more interactive and application-based assessments to better align with effective questioning practices.

School administrators should foster a supportive environment for ongoing teacher professional development. This includes creating platforms for collaborative learning where teachers can share effective instructional strategies. Administrators should also encourage a culture of experimentation in the classroom, allowing teachers to explore and refine various teaching methods. Recognizing the broader influences on effective teaching and learning, administrators may consider implementing comprehensive faculty training programs.

Teachers are encouraged to engage in continuous professional development, expanding their repertoire of instructional strategies beyond questioning techniques. Emphasis should be placed on creating a dynamic and interactive classroom environment that caters to diverse learning styles. Collaborative initiatives among teachers can facilitate the sharing of successful practices. Additionally, educators should reflect on their teaching methods, seeking ways to enhance student engagement and critical thinking through varied instructional approaches.

Learners should be encouraged to actively participate in classroom discussions and respond openly to different questioning techniques. Teachers can foster a culture of curiosity and critical thinking, emphasizing the importance of active engagement in the learning process. Learners should be made aware that academic success is influenced by various factors, motivating them to seek personalized learning strategies that align with their strengths and preferences.

For future researchers, it is recommended to delve deeper into the identified factors that influence effective teaching and learning in the context of Araling Panlipunan. Exploring additional variables beyond those considered in this study, such as classroom dynamics and instructional resources, could provide a more comprehensive understanding. Comparative studies across different educational settings may offer insights into the generalizability of the findings. Moreover, future research should consider longitudinal approaches to assess the long-term impact of various teaching strategies on student outcomes.

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